

Dynamic pricing in a frictional market under Dempster-Shafer uncertainty

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Introduction

One of the main hypotheses of classical no-arbitrage pricing theory is the absence of frictions in the market, which materializes in a discounted conditional expectation representation of price processes. Despite this simplifying assumption, it is well-known that real markets show frictions, most evidently in the form of bid-ask spreads (Amihud and Mendelson, 1986). Starting from Chateauneuf et al. (1996), a stream of research explored bid-ask pricing by relying on the Choquet expectation operator, mostly restricting to a single period (Cerrea-Vioglio et al., 2015). This contribution presents on-going research on dynamic bid-ask pricing.

Methods

We refer to the Dempster-Shafer theory (Shafer, 1976) which is a generalization of probability theory based on belief functions. In this framework, a notion of “imprecise” Markov and time-homogeneous process has been introduced in Cinfrignini et al. (2023b), under the name of DS-multiplicative binomial process. In turn, such process is associated with a conditional Choquet expectation operator. In case of a single frictional asset, the quoted paper proposes a dynamic bid-ask pricing rule which can be justified in terms of a generalized no-arbitrage condition (Cinfrignini et al., 2023a). Current research seeks efficient calibration techniques and extension to the multi-asset case.

Results

Referring to a single frictional asset, we propose an efficient calibration technique to produce a market-consistent dynamic bid-ask pricing rule. Furthermore, we consider the extension to the multi-asset case so as to face the pricing of more complex derivative contracts, like basket options. As a by-product, the resulting multi-variate DS-multiplicative binomial process induces a time-consistent dynamic coherent risk measure.

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